

Working Paper

Strategic Alignment in Program Management: A Framework for Sustainable Business Transformation

Adolfo M. Carreño ¹

September 2, 2024

Abstract

This paper explores the critical role of strategic alignment in program management as a driver of successful business transformation and long-term sustainability. In the current business environment, aligning program initiatives with overarching organizational goals optimizes resources, streamlines communication, and ensures that transformation efforts directly contribute to strategic objectives. Key drivers of strategic alignment, such as goal congruence, resource allocation, and risk management, are examined to highlight their role in fostering organizational cohesion and adaptability. The paper also addresses the challenges of achieving alignment, including organizational silos, cultural resistance, and the tension between short-term demands and long-term goals. To overcome these obstacles, recommendations include developing clear strategic objectives, implementing continuous monitoring and feedback mechanisms, and fostering leadership development and cultural change initiatives. Practical implications for business leaders and program managers are provided, offering actionable insights to enhance alignment within their organizations. Future research opportunities are suggested, focusing on the evolving nature of alignment in increasingly complex business environments, with an emphasis on emerging technologies and agile strategies. Ultimately, this paper underscores the importance of strategic alignment as a foundation for sustainable transformation and competitive advantage in program management.

Key Words:

Strategic alignment, program management, business transformation, organizational goals, resource allocation, risk management, leadership, stakeholder engagement, cultural change, long-term sustainability

¹ Institute for Change Leadership and Business Transformation
Email: acarreno@iclbt.org

I. Introduction

Strategic alignment within program management plays a crucial role in driving long-term business transformation. Achieving lasting success in a dynamic and complex business environment requires more than isolated project achievements or short-term wins. Organizations must ensure that their program initiatives are aligned with their broader strategic goals. When this alignment is in place, program management serves as a bridge, connecting individual projects to the organization's long-term objectives, resulting in a more cohesive approach to achieving meaningful outcomes. By aligning strategy with execution, resources are optimized, communication becomes more effective, and the desired business outcomes consistently support the company's vision.

However, many organizations struggle to realize the full potential of their transformation programs due to misaligned objectives. While businesses often invest considerable resources into these programs, the lack of alignment between individual initiatives and the overarching strategy leads to inefficiencies and missed opportunities. Short-term successes may be achieved, but without strategic alignment, these efforts rarely contribute to long-term growth or transformation. This disconnection between execution and strategy can result in wasted resources and unfulfilled objectives, undermining the potential for meaningful and sustainable change.

The complexity of modern business environments, where multiple initiatives run concurrently across various departments and locations, further complicates these challenges. Without clear alignment, transformation initiatives risk becoming fragmented, with outcomes that fail to support the organization's long-term vision. Therefore, it becomes essential for program management to act as a strategic function, ensuring that projects and programs are not only executed effectively but are also aligned with the organization's broader goals.

This paper is intended to show that strategic alignment in program management provides the framework necessary for turning individual efforts into cohesive, value-driven processes. By ensuring that all initiatives contribute to the organization's long-term strategy, program management plays a vital role in achieving sustainable transformation and lasting success. Through proper alignment, program managers can ensure that every project not only meets its specific objectives but also advances the organization's long-term vision, fostering continuous growth and maintaining a competitive advantage.

II. Theoretical Framework

Strategic Alignment in Business Context

Strategic alignment refers to the process by which an organization ensures that its resources, initiatives, and operations are cohesively aligned with its overarching goals and vision. The concept of strategic alignment is rooted in foundational theories in strategic management, notably Henderson and Venkatraman's Strategic Alignment Model (1994). This model emphasizes the need for a harmonious relationship between an organization's business strategy, its organizational processes, and the execution of projects and programs. In essence, strategic alignment ensures that every aspect of the organization—from individual tasks to large-scale programs—contributes to long-term value creation and competitive advantage (Tharp, 2007; Rahschulte, 2014).

Henderson and Venkatraman's model is particularly useful in program management, as it provides a framework for understanding how strategic goals can be translated into day-to-day operations. The model highlights the interconnectedness of business strategy and technology, asserting that alignment occurs not only at the operational level but also across the strategic, organizational, and technological dimensions. By using this model, organizations can systematically align their internal capabilities with external market opportunities, thereby ensuring that every initiative is relevant and value-driven.

In program management, strategic alignment plays a crucial role in ensuring that the organization's high-level goals are consistently reflected across various programs and projects. By bridging the gap between strategy and execution, the organization creates a clear framework for decision-making, resource allocation, and performance evaluation (Hamdan & Jaafar, 2014). This alignment prevents the inefficiencies and fragmentation that often arise when initiatives are disconnected from strategic priorities. Misalignment can lead to wasted resources, duplicated efforts, and projects that do not contribute to the organization's long-term objectives.

When effectively implemented, strategic alignment fosters coherence across all business operations, ensuring that every project and program is integrated into the broader organizational mission. This, in turn, promotes sustainability in business operations, as all initiatives work synergistically to support the organization's overarching goals (Ritson, Johansen, & Osborne, 2012). In a program management context, strategic alignment helps to maintain focus, optimize resources, and adapt to changes in the business environment, ensuring that transformation initiatives drive meaningful, long-term success.

The integration of Henderson and Venkatraman's model into program management allows organizations to better assess and align their strategic, organizational, and technological domains. This ensures not only smoother project execution but also the achievement of long-term strategic objectives, thereby embedding alignment into the essence of Organizations.

Program Management in Business Transformation

Business transformation refers to a comprehensive approach aimed at improving organizational performance through the adoption of new technologies, processes, and strategies that enable businesses to adapt to market shifts and maintain long-term competitiveness. As McKinsey (2023) defines it, business transformation focuses on key areas such as revenue growth, cost reduction, and customer satisfaction, requiring clear strategic goals, leadership, employee engagement, and strong governance. IBM (2024) expands on this by describing business transformation as the restructuring of business planning, operations, and customer experience to achieve strategic goals, emphasizing the importance of technology integration and data-driven strategies in driving innovation and improving competitiveness.

Figure 1
Components of Business Transformation

Within the context of business transformation, program management serves as a structured approach for managing multiple interconnected projects aimed at realizing strategic benefits that surpass the scope of individual initiatives (Project Management Institute, 2024; International Project Management Association, 2015). Unlike project management, which focuses on achieving specific outputs within a defined timeline and budget, program management coordinates various related projects to achieve long-term transformation objectives (Suvvari, 2022).

Figure 2
Project Management and Program Management Balance in the context of Business Transformation

Program management plays a critical role in guiding and structuring change initiatives, ensuring that these efforts align with the organization's broader strategic vision (BenMahmoud-Jouini & Charue-Duboc, 2022). This approach is particularly effective for managing complexity, as programs often involve multiple stakeholders, diverse teams, and significant resources across different departments. Through careful coordination and governance, program management helps organizations implement changes that not only deliver immediate benefits but also drive long-term transformation, minimizing risks while optimizing the use of resources (Rahschulte, 2014; Suvvari, 2022). This alignment with strategic goals is essential for sustaining competitiveness and ensuring that transformation efforts contribute to the organization's overall mission.

The Nexus Between Strategic Alignment and Program Management

The relationship between strategic alignment and program management is both profound and critical to achieving sustainable business transformation. Program management functions as the operational bridge that translates high-level strategic goals into actionable initiatives, while strategic alignment ensures that these initiatives are consistently advancing the organization's long-term objectives (Patel, 2013; Ritson et al., 2012). This connection enables organizations to navigate the complexities of transformation by aligning their execution capabilities with their broader strategic vision.

At its core, program management coordinates a portfolio of interrelated projects, ensuring that these projects not only meet their individual objectives but also contribute to the strategic goals of the organization. However, without strategic alignment, even well-executed programs may fail to deliver long-term value. Strategic alignment ensures that the outcomes of program initiatives are not isolated efforts, but part of a cohesive strategy that drives organizational growth and adaptation to market dynamics (Tharp, 2007). By aligning program management with strategic objectives, organizations create a feedback loop that continuously refines both project execution and strategic direction (Project Management Institute, 2021).

Strategic alignment plays a pivotal role in guiding program managers and teams by providing a clear framework for decision-making. When programs are aligned with organizational strategy, it enhances consistency across multiple projects, reducing redundancies and misalignment that can occur when individual project goals are disconnected from the company's broader vision (Rahschulte, 2014; Project Management Institute, 2024). This alignment offers clarity for leadership, enabling informed decisions regarding resource allocation, prioritization, and risk management. Leaders can ensure that resources are deployed to initiatives that directly support strategic goals, avoiding wasted effort and capital on projects that do not contribute meaningfully to long-term success.

Moreover, this strategic alignment fosters adaptability and responsiveness within the organization. As market conditions shift, aligned programs can quickly pivot or adjust to new priorities while remaining focused on the overarching strategic objectives. This dynamic adaptability is crucial in today's fast-evolving business environments, where static, short-term goals can be detrimental to long-term viability. Strategic alignment ensures that program management processes are not merely reactive but are designed to anticipate and adapt to both internal and external changes (Ritson et al., 2012).

The interplay between program management and strategic alignment creates a synergistic effect, ensuring that transformation efforts are not just focused on immediate gains but also on long-term sustainability. This integration allows for the development of a more coherent transformation roadmap, where all programs and projects are aligned with the organization's mission, vision, and strategic imperatives (Project Management Institute, 2024; International Project Management Association, 2015). Furthermore, the feedback mechanisms built into aligned program management allow for continuous assessment and recalibration of both strategic goals and program execution. This cyclical process enables organizations to remain agile, consistently fine-tuning their approach to transformation while ensuring alignment with strategic growth.

Figure 3

Strategic Alignment and Program Management Integration Stream

Ultimately, strategic alignment and program management are deeply intertwined, and their integration is essential for creating an environment where business transformations are not only efficiently executed but also sustainable in the long term. Through this alignment, organizations can ensure that each project and program contributes directly to their broader strategic objectives, fostering innovation, driving growth, and maintaining a competitive edge in the marketplace.

III. Strategic Alignment in Program Management: Critical Drivers

Strategic alignment is essential for ensuring that program management contributes meaningfully to an organization's long-term objectives. The key drivers that enable this alignment have been selected based on their fundamental impact on bridging strategy and execution. These drivers ensure that program management becomes a cohesive, value-driven process aligned with the organization's broader goals, rather than a series of disconnected projects.

In this section, the critical drivers—goal congruence and organizational cohesion, resource allocation and prioritization, and risk management and adaptability—are highlighted as they represent the essential elements needed for successful and sustainable transformation. These drivers are crucial since they address the core structural and operational aspects of program management that translate strategic objectives into coordinated, actionable initiatives.

Goal congruence ensures that all teams and departments are aligned with the organization's long-term objectives, fostering a shared vision that enhances collaboration and reduces the inefficiencies of fragmented efforts. Resource allocation is vital as it ensures that limited resources are directed toward initiatives that best support the organization's strategic goals. Misaligned resource distribution can result in wasted effort, while proper alignment ensures that resources are utilized effectively for maximum strategic impact. Lastly, risk management and adaptability play a central role in navigating the uncertainties of business transformation. Aligned risk management enables organizations to anticipate potential threats, while adaptability ensures that programs remain resilient and flexible in response to changing environments, without compromising on strategic objectives.

Figure 3
Critical Drivers of Strategic Alignment Stream

While other elements, such as technology or innovation, can act as important enablers, these three drivers form the foundation for strategic alignment. They address the broader systemic requirements needed for long-term transformation, ensuring that program initiatives are aligned with strategic priorities and contribute to sustainable organizational success.

Goal Congruence and Organizational Cohesion

Goal congruence is essential for ensuring that program management outcomes are aligned with the broader business strategy. It serves as the foundation for a unified organizational approach, where the objectives of individual projects and programs are in sync with the organization's overarching strategic goals. This alignment creates a clear and structured pathway toward achieving long-term success, enabling every department and team to focus their efforts on shared priorities. As a result, the risk of misaligned initiatives—which can lead to wasted resources, inefficiencies, and missed opportunities—is significantly reduced. When goal congruence is achieved, program management becomes a driving force for integrated business transformation, ensuring that all activities contribute meaningfully to the organization's strategic vision.

Fostering goal congruence requires more than simply aligning top-level objectives; it involves building a shared understanding of strategic priorities across all levels of the organization, from leadership to operational teams. This ensures that each department, regardless of its function, is working toward the same long-term goals. In doing so, program management not only aligns individual project outcomes but also integrates them into a cohesive transformation process that supports sustainable business growth.

Organizational cohesion plays a critical role in reinforcing goal congruence. It refers to the degree of collaboration and unity among different departments and teams within an organization. High cohesion enhances strategic alignment by fostering better communication, coordination, and resource sharing across the organization. Organizational silos, or isolated work units, are a common barrier to strategic alignment, often leading to fragmented efforts and conflicting objectives. However, when strategic alignment fosters organizational cohesion, these silos are broken down, and collaboration becomes the norm, allowing for more efficient and coordinated transformation efforts.

High levels of cohesion ensure that departments are not just functioning independently but are actively working together to achieve common objectives. This collaboration improves the flow of information across the organization, enabling teams to share resources, expertise, and best practices more effectively. As a result, transformation initiatives become more efficient, and the likelihood of achieving the organization's long-term vision increases. Furthermore, cohesion builds a sense of collective responsibility for achieving the organization's goals, enhancing motivation and accountability across teams. This shared commitment to the organization's success is crucial for driving large-scale transformations that require cross-functional cooperation.

Advanced technologies such as machine learning and automation can significantly enhance goal congruence across an organization. By utilizing real-time data-sharing platforms powered by artificial intelligence, organizations can ensure that every department aligns with the broader strategic goals. Predictive analytics can evaluate communication patterns and project workflows to detect early signs of misalignment. This early intervention capability allows for timely corrections, ensuring that all teams remain focused on shared objectives.

Furthermore, modern project management systems supported by intelligent technology can automatically track progress and provide insights on how individual projects align with overall goals. These tools allow program managers to identify potential divergences from strategic objectives and ensure that efforts remain cohesive across departments. By enhancing organizational cohesion with these advanced solutions, collaboration is improved, and strategic alignment is reinforced.

Figure 4

Goal Congruence and Organizational Cohesion Stream

Ultimately, goal congruence and organizational cohesion are interdependent drivers of successful business transformation. By ensuring that all teams are aligned and working together toward a unified vision, program management can lead to more efficient execution, better use of resources, and a stronger organizational focus on long-term success.

Resource Allocation and Prioritization

Aligning resource allocation with strategic priorities is a key driver of effective program management. Strategic alignment ensures that financial, human, and technological resources are deployed in a manner that directly supports the organization's long-term goals. Without this alignment, organizations risk misallocating resources to initiatives that do not contribute to overall business transformation or strategic objectives, leading to inefficiencies and diminished. By aligning resource allocation with strategic priorities, organizations can optimize their assets and drive more effective program execution.

Effective resource alignment requires a clear understanding of the organization's strategic goals as well as a continuous system for evaluating the impact of resource distribution. This means program managers must have mechanisms in place to assess how resources are being utilized and adjust allocations as needed to ensure that the highest-priority initiatives receive the necessary support. By doing so, organizations can ensure that their resources are directed toward value-generating activities that support sustainable growth.

When resource allocation is properly aligned with strategic priorities, transformation initiatives are more likely to be implemented efficiently and effectively. Programs that receive adequate resources are more capable of meeting their objectives, adhering to schedules, and staying within budget. Furthermore, strategic alignment in resource allocation enables organizations to be more adaptive in responding to changes in the business environment. As market conditions shift or new opportunities arise, resources can be reallocated swiftly to meet emerging needs without disrupting the overall transformation effort.

Modern Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools can optimize resource allocation by processing vast amounts of data to predict which resources should be directed to the most impactful initiatives. Through machine learning algorithms, organizations can assess historical project data, market trends, and strategic priorities to determine the best allocation of financial, human, and technological resources. This ensures that resource distribution supports long-term goals rather than being wasted on less critical activities.

Modern technology further aids in resource management by offering real-time updates, allowing organizations to dynamically adjust their resource allocation based on changing project demands or market conditions. This level of adaptability ensures that resources continue to support strategic objectives even as circumstances shift, maintaining alignment without disrupting operations.

Figure 5
Resource Allocation and Prioritization Stream

In essence, resource alignment provides the foundation for executing strategy at the program level. It ensures that all available assets are effectively utilized in a way that maximizes value and contributes to the long-term success of the organization. By continuously assessing and adjusting resource distribution, program management can ensure that transformation efforts remain focused, efficient, and resilient to changes in the external environment. This dynamic approach to resource allocation is critical for sustaining the momentum of transformation initiatives and achieving lasting success.

Risk Management and Adaptability

Strategic alignment plays a critical role in enhancing risk management processes within program management. By aligning initiatives with the organization's broader strategy, program managers are better equipped to identify potential risks early and mitigate them before they escalate into significant threats. When strategic objectives are clearly defined, it becomes easier to assess whether a particular risk jeopardizes the overall transformation effort or is confined to an individual project. This clarity allows for the prioritization of risks based on their potential impact on long-term organizational goals, ensuring that mitigation efforts are focused on the areas most critical to the success of the transformation.

In addition to improving risk management, strategic alignment also strengthens an organization's ability to adapt to a rapidly changing environment. Adaptability is a key enabler of successful business transformations, especially in dynamic industries where uncertainty and disruption are commonplace. When strategies are aligned across programs and projects, organizations can more easily adjust their plans and responses to unforeseen challenges or emerging opportunities without losing sight of the overarching business strategy. This alignment ensures that program managers can adapt their approaches effectively, allowing transformation efforts to remain relevant and resilient despite external shifts.

A well-aligned strategy not only enhances risk management by providing a framework for identifying and mitigating threats but also fosters flexibility in responding to changing conditions. This adaptability is essential for organizations aiming to sustain long-term success. In environments where market conditions or external factors can rapidly shift, strategic alignment provides the foundation for continuous adjustment while keeping the organization's transformation initiatives on track. By aligning risk management and adaptability with strategic goals, organizations ensure that their transformation initiatives are both robust and responsive, positioning them to thrive in the face of uncertainty.

Modern technology, particularly advanced analytics and machine learning systems, plays a crucial role in improving risk management within program management. By analyzing historical data and real-time trends, these systems can predict potential risks that might hinder transformation efforts. This proactive approach allows program managers to implement mitigation strategies before risks escalate, safeguarding the alignment of transformation initiatives with the organization's broader objectives.

Additionally, advanced technologies enable organizations to remain flexible in the face of external changes. Machine learning systems continuously analyze market shifts, customer behavior, and economic conditions, providing actionable insights that allow organizations to adapt their strategies without compromising long-term goals. This adaptability ensures that strategic initiatives remain on track, even in dynamic environments, reinforcing both resilience and responsiveness.

Figure 6

Ultimately, the combination of strategic alignment with risk management and adaptability allows organizations to navigate the complexities of transformation more effectively. By anticipating risks and remaining flexible in their execution, organizations can ensure that their long-term strategic goals are achieved while maintaining the resilience needed to handle unforeseen challenges. This holistic approach is critical for fostering sustainable transformation and long-term organizational success.

IV. Strategic Alignment: Facilitating Business Transformation

Strategic alignment is a critical enabler of successful business transformation, and organizations must undergo fundamental shifts in their strategy, culture, technology, and operations to remain competitive. However, transformation efforts that are not aligned with long-term strategic goals often fall short of achieving meaningful, sustainable results. To bridge this gap, program management plays a pivotal role in ensuring that each initiative is not only executed efficiently but also contributes to the organization's overarching vision.

Through alignment, businesses can create a clear roadmap for transformation, structuring resources, timelines, and priorities around sustainable outcomes. By embedding strategic alignment into program management, organizations can ensure that their transformation efforts are cohesive, efficient, and resilient, enabling them to adapt to evolving market conditions while staying focused on long-term success.

Business Transformation and Long-Term Goals

The success of business transformation hinges on aligning the transformation efforts with the organization's long-term strategic goals. This alignment ensures that the numerous projects and programs driving transformation are not standalone initiatives but part of a cohesive, strategic framework that directly contributes to the organization's broader objectives. Program management, when fully integrated with strategic vision, acts as the mechanism that operationalizes this alignment, ensuring that every initiative is geared towards achieving sustainable outcomes.

Strategic alignment in business transformation involves more than executing isolated improvements or adjustments; it requires a holistic approach where every project, process, and resource allocation serves the long-term vision of the organization. This alignment provides clarity, helping decision-makers prioritize initiatives that deliver the most significant strategic value. This process enables the efficient deployment of resources by ensuring that all efforts are focused on long-term impact rather than short-term wins, which may not contribute to the sustained success of the organization.

When program management is aligned with strategic goals, it provides a clear roadmap for transformation, allowing organizations to systematically tackle complex challenges. With this alignment, resources are allocated more effectively, timelines are structured to achieve long-term goals, and priorities are set based on strategic significance. This structure not only streamlines the execution of transformation initiatives but also enhances the organization's ability to remain agile and responsive to both internal and external pressures, such as market changes or technological advancements.

A key benefit of strategic alignment in program management is the ability to navigate the complexities inherent in large-scale transformations. Transformations often require coordination across multiple departments, each with its own set of goals and processes. Without alignment, these efforts can become fragmented, leading to inefficiencies and missed opportunities for synergy. When transformation programs are aligned with the strategic vision, they are more likely to contribute to innovation, growth, and competitive advantage, as they work together harmoniously rather than in isolation.

Moreover, strategic alignment allows organizations to adapt their transformation efforts in response to emerging opportunities or unforeseen challenges. In today's fast-evolving business landscape, agility is essential, and organizations must be able to adjust their course while remaining focused on their long-term objectives. Aligned program management ensures that shifts in strategy or operations do not derail the overall transformation but instead support its continued progress toward sustainable success.

By maintaining a strong connection between program management and strategic goals, organizations create a transformation process that is not only efficient but also resilient. This alignment fosters an environment where resources are used optimally, priorities are clear, and transformation efforts are fully integrated with the organization's long-term vision, resulting in a more successful and enduring transformation.

Real-World Examples of Strategic Alignment in Practice

Case study provide valuable insights into how strategic alignment in program management can drive successful business transformations. These case studies illustrate the benefits of aligning initiatives with broader organizational goals, resulting in long-term growth, innovation, and competitive advantage. However, they also highlight the potential pitfalls when this alignment is lacking, as seen in publicly known cases.

One prominent example of successful alignment is Domauto, an automotive supplier that integrated its exploration program with its parent company's strategic goals (BenMahmoud-Jouini & Charue-Duboc, 2022). Domauto's innovation efforts were closely aligned with the long-term objectives of the organization, allowing the company to leverage its exploratory projects for sustained technological advancements. By ensuring that the exploration program was not an isolated venture but instead directly contributed to the company's broader transformation strategy, Domauto was able to integrate cutting-edge technologies into its core operations. This strategic alignment positioned the company for long-term growth and market leadership, demonstrating how aligning innovation with strategic goals can lead to a significant competitive advantage.

Another notable example comes from the telecommunications industry in Kenya, where Osendi et al. (2024) detail how strategic alignment improved project performance in a rapidly evolving sector. The organization's transformation initiatives were closely guided by clearly defined strategic goals, ensuring that each project was aligned with the company's vision for growth and market expansion. This alignment facilitated a seamless connection between strategy and execution, enabling the organization to navigate the complexities of the telecommunications market effectively. As a result, the company successfully completed its transformation initiatives, which led to enhanced operational efficiency and profitability. This case underscores how maintaining strategic alignment enables organizations to adapt to dynamic industry environments while staying focused on long-term growth objectives.

On the opposite side, the case of Kodak offers a powerful example of the consequences of failing to align program management with strategic objectives. Kodak, once a dominant player in the photographic film industry, developed one of the first digital cameras in the 1970s but failed to align this innovation with its long-term strategic goals. The company chose to prioritize its traditional film business, delaying its transition to digital photography due to concerns that it would cannibalize its core product. This misalignment between innovation and strategy meant Kodak missed critical opportunities to lead in the digital era. As the digital camera and smartphone industries grew, Kodak's failure to adapt led to its eventual bankruptcy in 2012. This case exemplifies the risks of misaligned program management, where a lack of integration between innovation and strategic goals can result in a company's decline and loss of market relevance (Anthony, 2016).

These examples demonstrate both the benefits of aligning program management with strategic objectives and the dangers of failing to do so. Whether fostering technological innovation, improving operational efficiency, or expanding market reach, strategic alignment ensures that programs remain focused on delivering outcomes that support the organization's long-term vision. By integrating program initiatives with the company's strategic goals, organizations can achieve meaningful, sustainable transformations and position themselves for success in competitive and fast-changing markets.

The Role of Leadership and Stakeholder Engagement

Leadership is a fundamental driver in ensuring that strategic alignment is sustained throughout program management. Leaders are tasked with articulating the organization's strategic vision and ensuring that all programs and projects are aligned with these overarching goals. Effective leadership extends beyond setting direction; it empowers teams and program managers to make informed decisions that are aligned with long-term objectives. Leaders provide clarity on strategic priorities, fostering an environment where program management serves as an extension of the strategic framework rather than isolated efforts.

Leadership also plays a critical role in promoting organizational cohesion by establishing a culture of collaboration. Strong leaders break down silos between departments and encourage cross-functional cooperation to ensure that strategic objectives are consistently communicated across the organization. This collaborative environment helps to ensure that all initiatives are moving in tandem with the organization's long-term vision, reducing the risk of fragmented efforts that could undermine broader transformation goals. Leaders must also be adaptable, creating pathways for program managers to adjust strategies when faced with evolving challenges or opportunities, ensuring that flexibility does not come at the cost of alignment.

Stakeholder engagement is equally essential in maintaining strategic alignment. Engaging stakeholders early and consistently throughout the transformation process ensures that their needs, perspectives, and concerns are aligned with the organization's strategic goals. These stakeholders—whether internal teams, external partners, or customers—provide critical insights that guide decision-making, helping to refine programs and ensure that they continue to contribute to the broader organizational mission. By incorporating stakeholders into the process, organizations can anticipate potential challenges or misalignments and make adjustments before they affect program outcomes.

When stakeholders are actively involved in program management, they are more likely to feel a sense of ownership over the outcomes, which strengthens their commitment to the organization’s transformation objectives. This alignment between stakeholders’ expectations and the organization’s long-term strategy enhances collaboration and ensures that programs remain focused on delivering value. Furthermore, consistent engagement with stakeholders allows for continuous feedback loops, making it easier to adjust and refine programs in real-time.

Leadership and stakeholder engagement are deeply interconnected. Leaders not only facilitate the engagement of stakeholders but also rely on their input to drive alignment and inform strategic adjustments. Effective leaders create an environment where stakeholders feel empowered to share their insights and concerns, enabling the organization to remain agile while ensuring that long-term strategic objectives are met.

In summary, leadership and stakeholder engagement are critical to sustaining strategic alignment in program management. Leaders set the strategic vision and ensure cohesion across the organization, while engaged stakeholders provide the feedback and input necessary to adapt and refine programs. Together, these elements create a dynamic environment where strategic alignment can thrive, enabling organizations to achieve sustainable and successful transformations.

V. Challenges in Achieving Strategic Alignment

While strategic alignment is essential for ensuring that program management contributes to long-term business success, organizations often face significant challenges in maintaining this alignment. These challenges can arise from internal structural barriers, cultural resistance, or conflicting priorities that impede the seamless integration of program management with strategic objectives. Organizational silos, communication barriers, resistance to change, and the tension between short-term pressures and long-term goals are common obstacles that must be addressed to achieve effective alignment. Overcoming these challenges requires a coordinated effort from leadership, clear communication across departments, and the ability to balance immediate needs with future-oriented goals. In this section, the key hurdles to achieving strategic alignment are explored, along with strategies to mitigate their impact and ensure programs remain aligned with the organization’s broader vision.

Figure 7

Implications of Challenges in Strategic Alignment

Organizational Silos and Communication Barriers

One of the most significant challenges organizations encounter when attempting to achieve strategic alignment in program management is the existence of organizational silos. Silos form when different departments or teams operate in isolation, which leads to fragmented efforts that do not align with the broader organizational strategy. These silos create barriers to the free flow of information and collaboration, often resulting in misaligned goals and priorities. Rather than working collectively toward the organization's long-term objectives, individual departments may pursue their own localized agendas, leading to inefficiencies and missed opportunities for synergy.

Organizational silos not only impede communication but also create a culture of fragmentation, where departments or teams operate with limited understanding of how their actions impact the overall strategic vision. This lack of cohesion can lead to duplicated efforts, misallocation of resources, and ultimately, a failure to achieve the broader transformational goals of the organization. For example, if marketing and product development teams do not share a common strategic vision, their isolated efforts may result in products that do not align with market needs, thereby failing to meet organizational objectives.

To break down these silos and foster strategic alignment, a concerted effort to improve communication and collaboration across departments is essential. Effective communication ensures that all teams have a clear understanding of the organization's strategic goals and how their specific projects or programs contribute to achieving them. This requires not only regular updates but also creating an environment where information is shared freely across teams, without the constraints of hierarchical or departmental barriers.

Program managers play a critical role in bridging these gaps by establishing regular communication touchpoints, encouraging cross-functional collaboration, and creating transparency around decision-making processes and resource allocation. Through regular meetings, updates, and collaborative initiatives, program managers can ensure that different teams understand the broader strategic context of their work, helping them to align their efforts with the organization's long-term vision. Additionally, establishing governance frameworks that promote cross-departmental engagement can further reduce silos and enhance strategic coherence.

Breaking down communication barriers is not just about facilitating information exchange; it also involves fostering a culture of trust and collaboration, where departments see themselves as integral parts of a unified effort rather than as independent entities. Fostering structural and cultural changes that promote openness and cross-functional collaboration can significantly enhance alignment and the overall effectiveness of transformation initiatives. When departments work together toward shared objectives, the organization becomes more agile, efficient, and capable of sustaining long-term success.

In summary, overcoming organizational silos and communication barriers requires a comprehensive approach that involves improving both the structural and cultural dimensions of communication. By encouraging collaboration, establishing clear communication channels, and fostering a shared sense of responsibility toward strategic goals, organizations can ensure that their program management efforts are fully aligned with their long-term vision.

Cultural Resistance to Change

Organizational culture plays a pivotal role in determining whether efforts to align program management with business strategy will succeed or falter. Cultural resistance often emerges when transformation initiatives challenge long-standing norms, behaviors, or power dynamics within the organization. Ingrained habits and established processes can make employees and managers reluctant to adopt new strategies that may disrupt their familiar routines. This resistance is particularly pronounced when transformation efforts are perceived as threatening to the established order or when they require changes that shift authority or influence within the organization.

Cultural resistance is not just a matter of individual reluctance; it often stems from deeper systemic issues within the organization. When organizational culture is heavily rooted in rigid hierarchies or traditional practices, any attempt to realign program management with strategic goals can face significant opposition. Resistance may manifest as passive inertia, where employees comply with new initiatives without genuine commitment, or as active pushback, where key stakeholders may obstruct change efforts. Both forms of resistance can derail efforts to achieve strategic alignment, leading to inefficiencies, project delays, and missed opportunities for transformation.

To overcome this cultural resistance, organizations must foster an environment that embraces adaptability and openness to change. Leadership plays a crucial role in this process. Leaders must not only promote the importance of strategic alignment but also model the behaviors necessary for transformation to take root. Leadership's commitment to change must be visible and authentic, demonstrating that alignment with long-term strategic goals is not just a mandate but a shared organizational priority. By setting this example, leaders can inspire teams to actively engage in the transformation process rather than passively resist it.

In addition to strong leadership, actively involving employees in the transformation journey can help alleviate resistance. Providing clear communication about the strategic goals behind the change, offering training to equip employees with the necessary skills, and creating opportunities for feedback can foster a sense of ownership and reduce resistance. When employees understand the reasons behind strategic alignment and see how their roles contribute to the organization's broader objectives, they are more likely to embrace change and contribute to the alignment process.

Implementing structured change management frameworks is another critical strategy for addressing cultural resistance. These frameworks offer a systematic approach to navigating the emotional and behavioral challenges that often accompany transformation efforts. By breaking down the change process into manageable stages, organizations can guide employees through the transition, addressing concerns and challenges at each step. These frameworks help ensure that resistance is mitigated, and alignment is maintained as the organization moves toward its long-term goals.

Overcoming cultural resistance requires a multifaceted approach that includes strong leadership, employee engagement, and structured change management practices. By creating a culture that is open to change and aligning this cultural shift with the organization's strategic goals, businesses can reduce resistance and ensure that program management efforts contribute effectively to long-term success.

Balancing Short-Term Pressures with Long-Term Goals

One of the most significant challenges in achieving strategic alignment is managing the tension between short-term business pressures and the need to remain focused on long-term transformational goals. In many organizations, the urgency to deliver immediate results can result in decision-making that prioritizes short-term gains over the alignment with broader strategic objectives. This short-term focus can create a misalignment between the day-to-day execution of projects and the organization's long-term vision, as resources and attention are often diverted toward solving immediate business issues at the expense of sustainable progress.

Short-term pressures, driven by market conditions, stakeholder demands, or financial performance, can compel organizations to prioritize quick wins, which may lead to tactical successes but do little to support the larger transformation agenda. This imbalance can undermine strategic objectives, leading to a lack of coherence between projects and programs aimed at short-term goals and those intended to drive long-term organizational growth. Misallocation of resources or inconsistent project prioritization can further exacerbate this misalignment, reducing the overall impact of transformation efforts.

Successfully balancing these competing demands requires deliberate prioritization and careful decision-making. Program managers play a crucial role in this balancing act, ensuring that while short-term objectives are met, they do not derail the organization's long-term transformation goals. This can be achieved through the implementation of a robust strategic governance framework that provides flexibility to respond to immediate business needs while keeping long-term objectives in clear focus. Such governance structures ensure that program managers are equipped to adjust resources and priorities without losing sight of the larger transformation goals.

A continuous monitoring system is also vital to this balancing process. By tracking both short-term performance and progress toward long-term strategic goals, organizations can identify when and where adjustments need to be made to maintain alignment. Monitoring key performance indicators (KPIs) that reflect both immediate outputs and long-term outcomes allows leaders to make informed decisions, ensuring that short-term actions support, rather than conflict with, the organization's strategic vision. This ongoing assessment is critical for sustaining momentum in transformation efforts while managing the inevitable short-term challenges.

Leaders play a pivotal role in managing the balance between short-term execution and long-term strategy. Leadership is responsible for setting the tone and direction for both immediate performance and broader organizational transformation. By ensuring that immediate business pressures are addressed within the context of the organization's strategic goals, leaders can prevent short-term priorities from undermining the long-term transformation effort. Effective leaders must be able to navigate the trade-offs between the two and foster a culture that values both quick responsiveness and sustained progress toward strategic objectives.

Balancing short-term pressures with long-term goals requires a well-structured approach that includes governance frameworks, continuous monitoring, and strong leadership. By maintaining a focus on both immediate needs and broader strategic objectives, organizations can achieve alignment between day-to-day operations and long-term transformation, ensuring that short-term gains contribute to sustainable success.

VI. Recommendations for Strengthening Strategic Alignment

Achieving and maintaining strategic alignment requires more than just setting high-level goals; it demands a structured approach that permeates all levels of an organization. In order to strengthen alignment between strategic objectives and program management, organizations must focus on developing clear, actionable goals, implementing robust monitoring and feedback mechanisms, and fostering leadership and cultural change initiatives that support alignment. These recommendations provide a foundation for creating an environment where program management consistently drives transformation efforts that align with long-term organizational vision. By clarifying strategic objectives, continuously monitoring progress, and developing leaders who can guide these efforts, organizations can enhance their ability to navigate complex transformations and achieve sustainable success. In this section, specific strategies and practices are discussed to help organizations strengthen and sustain strategic alignment throughout the transformation process.

Figure 8
Stream for Strengthening Strategic Alignment

Developing Clear Strategic Objectives

A key step in reinforcing strategic alignment within an organization is the development and clear communication of strategic objectives. Without a unified understanding of the organization's long-term goals, program managers and teams may struggle to align their initiatives effectively. Strategic objectives serve as the foundation upon which alignment is built, guiding decision-making and execution across various departments. Leadership must take responsibility for defining these objectives in a manner that is both specific and actionable, ensuring that all levels of the organization understand their roles in achieving broader strategic goals.

The use of strategic tools, such as strategy maps, can help visualize the connection between high-level objectives and day-to-day activities, making these goals more accessible and actionable for program managers and teams. These tools allow leaders to communicate how specific projects contribute to long-term goals, ensuring that every team understands how their work impacts the overall direction of the organization. When objectives are represented visually, it simplifies the complex interplay between individual initiatives and strategic goals, promoting a clearer alignment across teams.

To maintain alignment, strategic objectives must be communicated effectively across all levels of the organization. This communication cannot be a one-time event but requires consistent reinforcement through regular reviews, updates, and transparent discussions. Regular strategic reviews and all-hands meetings are valuable practices to keep the entire organization focused on the overarching goals. These forums provide opportunities for leadership to revisit and, if necessary, refine objectives to ensure they remain relevant in the face of changing market dynamics or internal challenges.

Embedding strategic objectives into program and project charters is another practical way to ensure alignment during execution. By explicitly linking projects to the organization's long-term goals, program managers can ensure that teams remain focused on delivering outcomes that support the broader strategy. This practice not only provides clarity for teams but also enhances accountability, as each project is directly tied to measurable strategic objectives. Moreover, aligning objectives across projects ensures that resources are allocated effectively, further supporting the organization's overall vision.

Additionally, it is critical that organizations establish mechanisms to measure progress against these strategic objectives. Without measurable benchmarks, it becomes difficult for teams to gauge whether their efforts are contributing to long-term goals. By tracking performance through key performance indicators (KPIs) and other metrics, leaders can ensure that the strategic objectives remain front and center throughout the execution of programs. This approach also enables organizations to adjust their strategies dynamically, responding to new opportunities or challenges while maintaining a clear focus on long-term success.

Ultimately, the clarity and communication of strategic objectives are foundational to achieving and sustaining strategic alignment. By ensuring that these objectives are well-defined, consistently communicated, and embedded into daily activities, organizations can foster a unified approach to transformation efforts and enhance their ability to achieve long-term success.

Continuous Monitoring and Feedback Mechanisms

For organizations to sustain strategic alignment over time, implementing continuous monitoring and feedback mechanisms is essential. In today's dynamic business environment, where external factors such as market shifts, technological advancements, and evolving organizational priorities can quickly disrupt strategic objectives, regular assessment of alignment becomes critical. Continuous monitoring ensures that the organization remains flexible and adaptive, allowing program managers to make informed decisions that maintain alignment with long-term goals.

Program managers play a pivotal role in this process by using performance metrics and key performance indicators (KPIs) to track the progress of individual projects and assess their contribution to strategic objectives. KPIs provide measurable data on project performance, offering insights into how effectively resources are being used and whether outcomes are supporting the organization's long-term strategy. By tracking these metrics, organizations can quickly identify areas where projects may fall short of expectations and make timely adjustments to ensure continued alignment.

Beyond performance metrics, feedback from stakeholders at various levels within the organization is invaluable in ensuring that strategic alignment is maintained. Creating opportunities for periodic reviews, stakeholder surveys, and open forums enables teams and managers to share insights on how well programs are aligning with broader objectives. These feedback channels foster transparency and collaboration, ensuring that concerns or discrepancies are addressed early, and adjustments can be made proactively. Stakeholder involvement in these feedback loops also enhances engagement and ensures that program managers are not working in isolation but rather integrating diverse perspectives into the strategic alignment process.

Effective feedback loops not only allow for real-time adjustments but also create a culture of continuous improvement within the organization. These mechanisms enable teams to pivot quickly when misalignments are detected, ensuring that strategies remain relevant and responsive to emerging challenges and opportunities. By embedding continuous monitoring and feedback into the fabric of program management, organizations can enhance their ability to respond to change with agility and resilience.

Moreover, establishing a formal process for continuous learning from past performance and outcomes strengthens the alignment process. Lessons learned from both successful and underperforming initiatives can provide insights that help refine future strategies and improve decision-making at all levels. This continuous improvement cycle not only ensures that the organization remains aligned with its strategic goals but also promotes innovation and adaptability over time.

In conclusion, continuous monitoring and feedback mechanisms are integral to maintaining strategic alignment in the face of changing environments. By using performance metrics, encouraging stakeholder input, and fostering a culture of continuous improvement, organizations can ensure that their transformation efforts remain focused on achieving long-term objectives while adapting to evolving conditions.

Leadership Development and Cultural Change Initiatives

Leadership development is a cornerstone of fostering strategic alignment within program management. Effective leaders are the primary catalysts in driving an organization's strategic vision and ensuring its alignment across all levels. Their ability to communicate, inspire, and guide teams toward shared objectives is essential for maintaining this alignment throughout the organization. Leadership development programs, therefore, should not only focus on technical skills but also enhance leaders' ability to articulate long-term strategic goals and ensure that these goals are reflected in the day-to-day execution of programs and projects. Leaders who can connect high-level strategies with operational activities empower teams to stay focused on broader business objectives, creating a seamless alignment between vision and execution.

In addition to individual leadership development, organizations must recognize the critical role of cultural change initiatives in supporting strategic alignment. Organizational culture significantly influences how strategies are adopted, executed, and sustained. When cultural norms resist change, even the most well-designed strategies can fail to gain traction. Therefore, fostering a culture that embraces strategic alignment is imperative for long-term success. To build this culture, organizations should implement programs that encourage open communication, cross-departmental collaboration, and a shared commitment to the company's long-term vision. Cross-functional initiatives help to break down silos, enabling teams from different areas of the organization to align their efforts more cohesively, thereby enhancing strategic focus.

One effective way to embed cultural change is through structured change management frameworks. These frameworks guide organizations in managing the emotional and behavioral challenges that often arise during large-scale transformations. Cultural shifts, particularly in organizations that have long-standing operational norms, require careful navigation. By equipping managers and employees with change management training, organizations can mitigate resistance, encourage adaptability, and ensure that alignment efforts are smoothly integrated into the company's operations. Training programs should also emphasize leadership behaviors that promote a culture of open feedback, accountability, and alignment with strategic goals.

Leadership development and cultural change initiatives go hand-in-hand in creating an environment conducive to strategic alignment. While leaders set the tone and direction for alignment efforts, a culture that supports these efforts is equally important. Cultural change programs must foster an environment where strategic objectives are understood and embraced by everyone within the organization, from senior management to operational teams. This widespread cultural alignment ensures that employees are not only aware of the strategic vision but are actively contributing to its realization in their day-to-day work.

Ultimately, investing in leadership development and cultural change initiatives enables organizations to create a strong foundation for maintaining strategic alignment throughout the transformation process. Leaders and employees alike must be equipped with the skills and mindset needed to continuously align programs with the organization's long-term vision. When these initiatives are effectively implemented, organizations experience greater coherence in their program management efforts, resulting in more sustainable and successful business outcomes.

VII. Conclusion

Strategic alignment in program management is essential for driving successful and sustainable business transformation. By ensuring that all initiatives align with the organization's broader goals, businesses can optimize resources, improve communication, and foster long-term outcomes. Key drivers such as goal congruence, resource allocation, and risk management are pivotal in promoting cohesion, efficiency, and adaptability. Leadership and stakeholder engagement remain crucial in supporting these efforts.

However, organizations face persistent challenges, including communication silos, cultural resistance, and balancing short-term pressures with long-term goals. Overcoming these barriers requires a comprehensive approach that clarifies strategic goals, implements continuous monitoring, and invests in leadership development.

As businesses continue to navigate digital transformation and increasing emphasis on sustainability, strategic alignment becomes even more important. Emerging technologies, such as AI and data analytics, must be integrated with alignment strategies to maintain competitiveness. Additionally, aligning program management with Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) standards enhances long-term resilience and responsible business practices.

In this evolving business landscape, strategic alignment will bridge technological advancements and sustainable growth. Organizations that prioritize alignment in program management will be better positioned to adapt, innovate, and thrive. Embedding alignment into transformation strategies creates pathways to growth, competitive advantage, and enduring success.

Implications for Future Research and Practice

Several promising avenues for future research could further illuminate the role of strategic alignment in successful business transformation. One key area of exploration is the impact of emerging technologies—such as advanced artificial technologies, data analytics, and machine learning—on alignment processes. These tools provide opportunities for real-time monitoring, enabling organizations to dynamically adjust programs as new data emerges. Through real-time data analysis, decision-makers can immediately assess how well ongoing initiatives align with long-term goals, making swift course corrections and improving responsiveness.

Future research could also focus on how advanced technologies enable predictive analytics, shifting alignment management from reactive to proactive. By anticipating potential misalignments, organizations can allocate resources more effectively and adjust strategies before challenges escalate. This proactive approach could redefine how businesses maintain strategic coherence in fast-paced, volatile environments.

In addition, researchers should examine how strategic alignment frameworks must evolve to address increasingly complex and dynamic business conditions. As organizations become more interconnected and face unpredictable external forces, agility and resilience must be incorporated into alignment strategies. Future studies could explore how alignment frameworks can adapt to support ongoing innovation while maintaining coherence with long-term strategic goals.

On a practical level, business leaders and program managers should prioritize integrating modern technologies into their alignment processes. This includes investing in leadership development programs that prepare leaders to leverage advanced technologies for enhanced decision-making and real-time alignment tracking. Additionally, fostering a culture of flexibility and collaboration will help organizations remain agile and responsive, ensuring that alignment remains consistent even as external conditions shift.

By focusing on strategic alignment and harnessing emerging technologies, organizations can achieve more adaptive transformations while positioning themselves for sustained competitive advantage and long-term growth. As global business environments become increasingly digital and data-driven, maintaining alignment between strategy and execution will be essential for achieving lasting success in a highly competitive marketplace.

References

- Anthony, S. D. (2016, July 15). Kodak's downfall wasn't about technology. *Harvard Business Review*. <https://hbr.org/2016/07/kodaks-downfall-wasnt-about-technology>
- Araujo, M., Storopoli, J., & Rabechini Jr., R. (2021). Project portfolio management and information technology strategic alignment. *International Journal of Innovation and Technology Management*, 18(8), 2150042. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0219877021500425>
- BenMahmoud-Jouini, S., & Charue-Duboc, F. (2022). Integration of an exploration program with its parent organization: A lifecycle perspective. *International Journal of Project Management*, 40(5), 587-597. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2022.05.006>
- Bröchner, J. (2022). Project tragedies. *International Journal of Project Management*, 40(4), 467-470. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2022.04.001>
- Ershadi, M. J., Edrisabadi, R., & Shakouri, A. (2020). Strategic alignment of project management with health, safety and environmental management. *Built Environment Project and Asset Management*, 10(1), 78-93. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BEPAM-03-2019-0023>
- Hamdan, Y., & Jaafar, K. (2014). *Strategic alignment of projects: Evaluation and selection process*. Paper presented at PMI® Global Congress 2014—EMEA, Dubai, United Arab Emirates. Newtown Square, PA: Project Management Institute.
- Haniff, A. P., & Galloway, L. (2022). Modeling strategic alignment in project networks. *International Journal of Project Management*, 40(5), 517–530. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2022.05.001>
- Henderson, J. C., & Venkatraman, N. (1994). Strategic alignment: A model for organizational transformation via information technology. In M. S. Scott Morton & T. J. Allen (Eds.), *Information technology and the corporation of the 1990s* (pp. 202–220). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780195068061.003.0009>
- IBM. (2024). *What is business transformation?* IBM. <https://www.ibm.com/topics/business-transformation>
- International Project Management Association (IPMA). (2015). *IPMA individual competence baseline: Version 4.0*. International Project Management Association.
- Jacobsson, M., & Söderholm, A. (2022). An essay on Homo Projecticus: Ontological assumptions in the projectified society. *International Journal of Project Management*, 40(3), 315-319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2021.11.004>
- Karayaz, G., & Gungor, O. (2013). *Strategic alignment and project management offices: Case studies from successful implementations in Turkey*. In Proceedings of the 46th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.1109/HICSS.2013.499>
- McKinsey & Company. (2023, April 17). *What is business transformation?* McKinsey & Company. <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/mckinsey-explainers/what-is-business-transformation>
- Martinsuo, M., & Anttila, R. (2022). Practices of strategic alignment in and between innovation project portfolios. *Project Leadership and Society*, 3, 100066. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plas.2022.100066>
- Osendi, A., Ndururi, M., Sagasi, T., & Mutua, J. (2024). Strategic alignment and project performance in the telecommunication industry in Kenya. *East African Scholars Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 7(5), 172-177. <https://doi.org/10.36349/easjebm.2024.v07i05.003>
- Patel, D. (2013). *Strategic alignment: The connecting link between strategy and execution*. Paper presented at PMI® Global Congress 2013—North America, New Orleans, LA. Newtown Square, PA: Project Management Institute.
- Project Management Institute. (2021). *A guide to the project management body of knowledge (PMBOK® Guide) – Seventh edition and the standard for project management*. Project Management Institute.

- Project Management Institute. (2024). *The standard for program management (5th ed.)*. Project Management Institute.
- Rahschulte, T. (2014). *Aligning execution and strategy through program management*. Paper presented at PMI® Global Congress 2014—North America, Phoenix, AZ. Newtown Square, PA: Project Management Institute.
- Ritson, G., Johansen, E., & Osborne, A. (2012). Successful programs wanted: Exploring the impact of alignment. *Project Management Journal*, 43(1), 21-36. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pmj.20273>
- Rosselet, U., & Wentland, M. (2011). Strategic alignment and IT project portfolio management. *The International Journal of Knowledge, Culture and Change Management: Annual Review*, 10(7), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.18848/1447-9524/CGP/v10i07/49991>
- Suvvari, S. K. (2022). Project portfolio management: Best practices for strategic alignment. *Innovative Research Thoughts*, 8(4), 372-384. <https://doi.org/10.36676/irt.v8.i4.1476>
- Tharp, J. (2007). *Align project management with organizational strategy*. Paper presented at PMI® Global Congress 2007—EMEA, Budapest, Hungary. Newtown Square, PA: Project Management Institute.
- Zhang, D., Guo, P., & Zhao, J. (2022). The motives system for developing project-based inter-organizational cooperation. *International Journal of Project Management*, 40(2), 167-180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2021.11.010>